

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND FITNESS SMARTPHONE APPS USE IN HEALTHY PEOPLE: AN EXPLORATORY ANALYSIS WITHIN THE DARE PROJECT

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PURPOSE

The purpose of this study is to explore the existing smartphone apps aimed at increasing PA/fitness level in healthy populations.

This review is performed within the PNRR Project DARE (DigitAl lifelong pRevEntion), aimed at developing digital tools to monitor lifestyles (including PA) and implementing interventions for primary prevention.

RESULTS

A total of 20 papers were finally included (Fig.1). The n. of interventions describing only stand-alone apps in the included SRs ranged from 1 to 8, with totally 42 different apps found. In this work, only the 12 smartphone apps with built-in sensors are reported (Table 1) and considered for further description. All the retrieved apps were effective in increasing PA/fitness. The main app characteristics are shown in Fig.2.

The following aspects are to be evidenced: no apps targeted to children; missing apps tested in various wide world areas; few apps with multiple sensors; few apps reporting sedentary outcomes (together with PA outcomes); less than half apps validated; behavior change techniques (BCT) not reported in more than half studies.

METHODS

A systematic review (SR) was conducted on Pubmed/Medline targeting SRs and meta-analyses (MAs) published in the years 2015-2023, that investigated effectiveness of stand-alone smartphone apps with PA/fitness measures as primary or secondary outcomes in healthy populations aged 6-65 years.

Figure 1: Flow diagram of SRs and MAs

Figure 2: Characteristics of the retrieved smartphone apps with built-in sensors (n=12).

Table 1: Smartphone apps with built-in sensors retrieved in the Pubmed/Medline SR.

APP NAME	SR of reference	Papers associated
Accupedo pedometer app	Domin 2021, Elavsky 2019, Feter 2019, Islam 2020, Laranjio 2020, Lee 2018, Negreiros 2022, Romeo 2019	Walsh 2016, Glynn 2013, Glynn 2014
Active 10 app	Brannan 2019	Ciravegna 2019
Analytic, social and affective apps	Elavsky 2019, Dehghan 2022, Domin 2021, Lee 2018	King 2013, King 2016
bActive app	Domin 2021, Elavsky 2019, Laranjio 2020	Harries 2013, 2016
CalFit app (California family fitness)	Stecher 2023	Zhou 2018
Carrot Rewards App	Feter 2019	Mitchell 2018
Moves app	Laranjio 2020	Patel, 2018, 2017, 2016a, 2016b
MyBehavior app	Domin 2021, Elavsky 2019, Laranjio 2020	Rabbi 2015
SitCoach app (Simple Intelligence Training)	Domin 2021	Van Dantzig 2013
Smartphone pedometer app	Elavsky 2019	Fong 2016
Strive app	Elavsky 2019	Vathsangam and Sukhatme, 2014
UOIFit	Domin 2021, Langarizadeh 2021, Quelly 2015	Lu 2013, 2014

CONCLUSIONS

From this first exploratory analysis, some needs emerge from the literature. Future research on apps with built-in sensors should imply: targeting children aged 6-13; incorporating multiple sensors in the smartphone to collect multiple data with one app in wide populations; increasing sedentary-related outcomes to be collected in the app; validating the smartphone sensor against gold standard tools; basing the interventions on BCTs.

Further searches in other databases are envisaged to catch other valuable apps, and a deeper analysis is needed to detail characteristics of the single apps, such as user ratings/usability or technical features. All these aspects will be considered in the DARE project, in order to develop digital tools that can be effective, valid, user-friendly, applicable to huge populations and that can simultaneously collect different PA-related and sedentary-related data.